

Deliverable 2.2

Report on matching biogenic flows with certification systems

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info@star4bbs.eu

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AUTHORS

Olaf Porc, NOVA

Luciano Proto Cassina, NOVA

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Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Olaf Porc	NOVA
Luciano Proto Cassina	NOVA

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Luana Ladu	TUB
Nikola Matovic	TUB
Stamatia Skoutida	AUA

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Partners short names

TUB	Technische Universitat Berlin
UNITELMA	Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma
UNI	Ente Italiano di Normazione
AUA	Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon
USC	Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
NOVA	Institut for politische und Okologische Innovation GMBH
BB	Better Biomass
BAM	Bundesanstalt fuer Materialforschung und Pruefung
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association
ISEAL	Iseal Alliance

Abbreviations

STAR4BBS	Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems
SCS	Sustainability Certification Schemes
B2B	Business-to-Business
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
FAOSTAT	FAO Statistical Databases
UNCTD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
UN	United Nations
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne
JRC	Joint Research Centre
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Waste
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
WP	Work Package
WP2	Work Package 2
D2.4	Deliverable 2.4
D2.5	Deliverable 2.5

Executive Summary

This report is a key component of the Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems (STAR4BBS) project. The main objective of the STAR4BBS project is to harness the potential of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and labels to facilitate a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. This includes the development of indicators and an innovative monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, as well as business-to-business (B2B) labels relevant for biogenic feedstocks, bio-based materials and products.

The establishment of a comprehensive monitoring system for assessing the robustness and effectiveness of bio-based SCS and labels requires an important preliminary step: a systematic review of information related to existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels and their relevance for biogenic feedstocks and bio-based materials and products. At the heart of this effort is the identification and verification of relevant feedstocks and bio-based intermediates, materials and products flow within the European bioeconomy. To achieve this, the objective of Work Package 2 of the STAR4BBS project is to collect accurate global trade data and information on the volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based materials imported into the EU in order to identify the most relevant biomass flows. Furthermore, the aim is to provide a comprehensive overview of certified and non-certified biomass flows, thus contributing significantly to the assessment of the impact and contribution of sustainability certification and labelling schemes. The resulting findings, combined with further research on certified and uncertified trade flows and the impacts, costs and benefits of certification and labelling, will improve understanding of the potential of these schemes to support policy and industry sustainability objectives. It will also facilitate greater awareness of the differences between different certification schemes.

In this context, the main focus of this deliverable D2.2 is to outline a conceptual framework and methodology for linking the certification schemes and labels considered in Tasks 1.2 and Task 1.3 with the biomass trade flows identified in Task 2.1. The objective is to deliver an initial overview of the share of certified and non-certified biogenic feedstock and bio-based products in the European bioeconomy at the end of the analysis in Work Package 2. This methodology provides a preliminary overview that is limited by its reliance on numerous assumptions and simplifications. As a result, its results may not be precisely accurate. Initial research suggests that there are significant challenges in obtaining data and information on the certification status of biogenic feedstocks and specific bio-based products, with availability often limited or difficult to find. While certification schemes and labels may indicate that a product is certified, along with accompanying documentation, there is often a lack of information of the proportion of feedstock and/or bio-based products that are actually certified on the market. The most accessible information is usually available from certification bodies specialising in specific feedstocks (e.g., FSC/PEFC for wood, Bonsucro for sugar cane), which can provide details of certified cultivation by region. Based on this database, any analysis of certified and non-certified status is performed at the feedstock level using the Chain of Custody model, specifically the mass balance approach, along the value chain.

The availability of data from different certification databases and the inclusion of reasonable assumptions are critical to the design of the methodology, but as mentioned above, due to their limited availability and simplification, they can only provide a first orientation. However, beyond the scope of the project, this methodology could serve as a starting point and be used, adapted and extended in future models.

The bio-based industry plays a crucial role in the transition to a more sustainable and circular economy. It spans several sectors, including agriculture, forestry, chemicals, plastics and textiles (Porc et al. 2022). The industry is characterised by the use of biological feedstocks, such as crops, wood as well as organic feedstocks from processing industries and waste streams to produce a wide range of materials and products. As a result, it has the potential to make a significant contribution to sustainability goals such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving resource efficiency and promoting the circular economy. It can also have a positive impact on socio-economic objectives such as local development through the use of regional resources and the creation of green jobs.

However, the use of bio-based feedstocks needs to be carefully regulated and controlled to mitigate negative environmental and social impacts, such as deforestation, soil erosion, biodiversity loss and the exploitation of child labour in developing countries (Bauchmüller et al. 2021; Weiss et al. 2012).

To facilitate this transition and ensure the credibility of sustainability claims, Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels serve as critical tools (Ladu and Blind 2017). They provide independent verification and validation of sustainability efforts and promote transparency and accountability throughout supply chains. However, these SCS face challenges such as limited scope, high costs and lack of harmonisation, with the latter being the main drawback (Mori Junior et al. 2016).

There are currently a large number of SCSs and labels in the European Union, each with its own set of criteria and standards. This large number can lead to confusion among businesses and consumers, as well as increased operational costs for businesses operating in several countries and seeking regional or national certification (Mori Junior et al. 2016). Businesses are often burdened with providing documentation to demonstrate compliance with different criteria. For consumers, the proliferation of labels with different criteria and standards makes it difficult to make informed choices.

The STAR4BBS project aims to overcome these problems and maximise the potential of sustainability certification schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to a sustainable bio-based economy. The STAR4BBS project focuses on the development of indicators and a new monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes and B2B labels for organic raw materials and bio-based materials and products. This information will provide the basis for much-needed harmonisation between SCS, leading to increased transparency of global and EU trade flows.

At the start of the project, we initiated the collection and systematic analysis of trade flow data. This formed the basis of the project's analysis and strategic approach, which aims to gain an accurate understanding of the current state of the European bioeconomy. Within Work Package 2, specific tasks include the collection of data and information on the volume of biological raw materials and bio-based materials and products in global trade flows, with a focus on distinguishing between certified and non-certified biomass flows. The research focus on imports to and exports from the EU, taking into account the geographical distribution. The aim is not only to understand the

existing biomass flows in the European bioeconomy, but also to provide a first overview of the share of certified biogenic flows, intermediate and final bio-based product flows. It also highlights the potential impact of certification schemes on sustainability goals, including differences between different SCSs.

This deliverable presents a first concept and methodology for linking certification schemes and labels with biomass trade flows. It aims to provide a first overview of the share of certified and non-certified bio-based raw materials and products in Europe. The analysis mainly follows the mass balance approach, a chain of custody model. In this model, the volume of certified product entering the operation is controlled so that an equivalent volume of product leaving the operation can be marketed as certified. Physical mixing of certified and non-certified products is allowed but not mandatory at any stage of the production process, provided that the quantities are documented and controlled (ISEAL Alliance 2016). While the proportion of specified characteristics in the input may only match initial proportions on average and can vary across outputs, it's assumed the proportion of certified vs. non-certified flow remains consistent throughout the value chain. Thus, while the real composition of one final product isn't guaranteed, the composition across all final products is considered.

The main focus of this report is to develop a measurement approach to link sustainable certification systems and labels to biomass trade flows in order to determine the proportion of certified and uncertified biomass flows. The first steps include the selection of suitable bio-based value chains for assessment against specific criteria, with at least 15 chains selected. In addition, the ongoing analysis of trade flow data in Task 2.1 will provide an overview of the trade in raw materials and bio-based products, including their importers in Europe. These biogenic flows will then be combined with the results of the certification scheme reviews in Tasks 1.2 and 1.3 of the STAR4BBS project to allocate biomass to the respective certification schemes. The last section describes the mass balance approach and explains how it attempts to match biogenic flows and certification schemes (2.2

Mass balance approach). Finally, a short conclusion is drawn.

The importance of this work lies in its future application within the STAR4BBS project, in particular in WP2, where the developed concept will support the ongoing analysis of trade flows. In particular, it will contribute to the "Report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products and material (D2.4)" to be delivered in project month 24. D2.4 will present the final results of the trade flow analysis (Task 2.1) together with the results of the certification level analysis to provide an initial overview of the shares of certified and non-certified bio-based raw materials and products in Europe (Task 2.2). In addition, these results could also feed into the report "Impact assessment of the SCS on market access and trade" (D2.5). This assessment will look at the impact of sustainability certification on market access and trade for bio-based resources and products, and whether sustainability certification acts as a catalyst or a barrier. Insights into certified and non-certified flows could demonstrate the impact of certified flows compared to non-certified flows. Beyond the scope of the project, this methodology could serve as a first approach of its kind and be used, modified and extended in future works and models.

2 Methodology for assessing certified and non-certified biomass trade flows

The following section describes the methodology developed to match biogenic flows with certification schemes and to obtain a detailed overview of the share of certified and non-certified bio-based feedstocks and products traded into and within Europe. The proposed methodology consists of different steps, as shown in Figure 1.

Initially, the process of selecting relevant bio-based supply chains is underway, with the aim of evaluating at least 15 of these supply chains. At least 10 biogenic feedstocks and at least 5 bio-based products should be considered. For this reason, the selection is divided into a selection of bio-based feedstocks and a selection of bio-based products. The selection of suitable feedstocks has been completed and the results are presented in section 2.1.3. The process of choosing five bio-based products and completing the value chain selection is ongoing and will be continued in the coming weeks. The selection criteria for both processes are outlined in the following paragraphs.

It should be noted that in Work Package 2 of the STAR4BBS project, bio-based value chains are or were selected for the assessment of certified and non-certified biogenic trade flows as well as for the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) in Work Package 5 (Task 2.3; Deliverable 2.3). Due to partially different selection criteria, there may be differences in the selection of value chains considered between the two analyses. To avoid confusion, this report will use the term 'test case selection' when referring to value chain selection for cost-benefit analysis.

Both selections are based on the availability of feedstocks and use data and figures from the results of the ongoing trade flow analysis (Task 2.1) as a basis for their evaluation. However, the selection of test cases for the cost-benefit analysis focused more on the inclusion of residual biomass flows and waste in order to promote closed value chains in the context of the circular economy. Another focus was on the optimal feedstock composition for efficient biomass processing in a biorefinery. In addition, the selection of test cases excluded feedstocks such as palm oil due to growing environmental concerns. However, such environmental concerns will not play a role in the selection of value chains for determining the certification share.

The next step will be to combine the identified biogenic flows from Task 2.1 with the results of the certification schemes from Tasks 1.2 and 1.3. The focus will be on matching biomass flows with corresponding certification schemes. To this end, the input from the trade data analysis of Task 2.1 will be used to provide a comprehensive overview of the trade in feedstocks and bio-based products and their importers in Europe.

Finally, an approach to aligning bio-based material flows with certification schemes and how they could be described along the value chain using the mass balance approach is outlined. It is crucial to establish initial rough values and information on the certification share based on the certifiers' databases and available documentation as well as additional supporting literature and expert knowledge.

Figure 1: Overview of methodological steps used for quantification of certified and non-certified biomass flows

2.1 Value chain selection

In order to quantify the certified and non-certified share of bio-based trade flows in the EU, relevant bio-based value chains are currently being selected. The aim is to assess at least 15 bio-based supply chains (including at least 10 biogenic raw materials and at least 5 bio-based products). The selection of value chains is done in two steps. First, suitable feedstocks have been identified based on criteria and trade data, the results of which are presented in this report. Second, the selection of 5 bio-based products and thus the completion of the value chain selection will follow in the coming weeks of the project.

2.1.1 Feedstock selection

For the identification of suitable feedstocks for the desired bio-based value chains in the European bioeconomy, reference is made to the descriptions provided in Deliverable 2.1 (Porc and Proto Cassina 2023). This report illustrates the diversity of feedstocks used in the EU bioeconomy from different origins. In order to streamline the process, these feedstocks relevant to EU-based industries are categorised according to their respective economic sectors - classified as primary, secondary and tertiary feedstocks. These bio-based feedstocks are considered suitable for integration into the European bioeconomy sectors. Table 1 provides an overview of the relevant feedstocks considered in Deliverable D2.1.

Table 1: Classification according to the economic sector of production of the most relevant EU bio-based feedstocks for the EU bio-based industry

Sector	Origin	Grown feedstock and its residues	Waste
Primary sector	Agriculture and horticulture	Sugar: sugar beet Starch: Wheat, maize, barley, oat, potato Oil: Rape, sunflower, olives Fibres: Flax, hemp Miscellaneous: Miscanthus Residues from agriculture and horticulture, Food loss in the field	
	Forestry	Spruce, beech, silver birch, ash, scots pine, oak, douglas fir, sycamore, short rotation crops, plant resins, cork Residues from forestry	
	Aquatic feedstock (fisheries, aquaculture, algae)	Micro- and macroalgae Residues from fisheries (e.g., by-catch) Residues from aquaculture Algae leftovers	
Secondary sector	Processing, food industry, textile industry	Residues from forest-based industries (e.g., woodworking facilities, construction), pulp & paper Residues from sugar, starch or oilseeds processing Residues from fermentation processes Residues from meat, poultry and fish processing industries (fat, bones, skin, etc.) (Depending on value) Biogenic gases generated from industrial processes or bioenergy plants	Industrial wastewater and sludge, Recycled paper Animal manure
		Leftovers, textile residues	Textile waste (separately collected in clothing bin)
Tertiary sector, Municipalities, Households	Wholesale and retail, restaurants, hotels, catering		Bio-waste (incl. consumer food waste), sewage sludge and waste water from municipalities, textile waste (not separately collected)

The ongoing biomass trade flow analysis from Task 2.1 is a key resource for the feedstock selection process. This analysis provides detailed global trade data and insight into the quantities of biogenic feedstocks imported into the EU. It is crucial for identifying the most relevant biomass flows to be considered. The analysis of biogenic feedstocks has already been completed and documented in Deliverable D2.1. Market databases such as the FAO's FAOSTAT database or the UN's Comtrade (UNCTD) were used to guarantee comprehensive coverage and reliable data sources.

A comprehensive assessment framework has been employed to identify the most suitable feedstocks, considering factors such as import volumes and availability within the EU. Additionally, the relationship between domestic production in the EU and identified import volumes has been examined to illustrate the import dependency of biogenic feedstocks. However, this approach may result in some feedstocks not being included (e.g. from aquaculture). Nonetheless, there were compelling reasons to include feedstocks from as many categories as possible, even if they deviated from the original selection criteria.

Including all major feedstock sectors allows for a more thorough assessment of available biomass sources and ensures that potentially valuable resources are not overlooked. In addition, the deliberate inclusion of different feedstock categories helps to diversify the feedstock base for bio-economic value chains.

In order to meet the requirement to include at least 10 bio-based feedstocks, specific amounts were chosen for different feedstock categories: four agricultural feedstocks (one each for starch crops, sugar crops, oil crops and fibre crops). For the forestry and aquaculture categories, there is only one major feedstock considered representative of the sector (forestry: wood; aquaculture: algae), with no other viable options within these specific categories. To meet the requirement of at least 10 bio-based feedstocks, an additional four residual feedstocks from processing industries and wastes were selected.

Feedstocks have been selected from the following sectors:

- *Agricultural feedstocks (4 Feedstocks)*
 - *Starch crop (1 Feedstock)*
 - *Sugar crop (1 Feedstock)*
 - *Vegetable oil crop (1 Feedstock)*
 - *Fiber crop (1 Feedstock)*
- *Forestry feedstock (1 Feedstock)*
- *Aquaculture feedstock (1 Feedstock)*
- *Residual feedstocks from processing industry + wastes (4 Feedstocks)*

Given the diversity of feedstocks in the agricultural and secondary feedstock categories, a scoring system was introduced to streamline the selection process. This scoring mechanism facilitated the identification of optimal choices within each feedstock category. The evaluation based on this scoring system has already been completed and is presented in section 2.1.3.

Table 2 below outlines the criteria and scoring system used in the feedstock selection evaluation:

Table 2: Value chain selection – selection criteria + scoring system for selecting feedstock

Category	Criterion	Points					
		5 Points	4 Points	3 Points	2 Points	1 Point	0 Points
Feedstocks	Volume of imports into the EU	> 5 million tonnes	2 - 5 million tonnes	1 - 2 million tonnes	0.5 - 1 million tonnes	0.1 - 0.5 million tonnes	No imports
	Import dependence of the EU	100%	75% - 99%	50% - 74%	25% - 49%	Less than 25%	
	Availability in the EU (domestic production + imports – exports)	> 100 million tonnes	50 - 100 million tonnes	10 - 50 million tonnes	1 - 10 million tonnes	Less than 1 million tonnes	Not available

Following the selection of feedstocks, the next step was to identify possible value chains. This task was carried out through literature reviews and desktop research as described in Deliverable 2.1. The aim was to identify value chains using bio-based feedstocks in the industrial sectors of the European bioeconomy. Numerous value chains based on biogenic raw materials were identified, as well as a wide variety of different raw materials, processes, intermediate and final products and sectors in the bio-based value chains. In addition, there is a significant diversity of supply chains within each sector (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4)

Figure 2: Industrial Material use of Biomass in Europe in 2015 (nova-Institut GmbH 2015)

Figure 3: Bio- and CO₂-based Economy: Feedstocks, Processes and Products (nova-Institut GmbH 2023)

Figure 4: Pathways to bio-based polymers (nova-Institut GmbH 2022)

At the end of this methodological step, there is a comprehensive list of simplified value chains (from feedstock to intermediate products to final products). Figure 5 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a screenshot of an excerpt from the Excel spreadsheet with examples of value chains created based on the evaluated feedstocks and information from the literature and desktop research.

Feedstock Sector	Raw Biomass	Primary & Secondary feedstocks	Bio-based intermediate product	End-Product
Agriculture	Palm Oil	Vegetable Oil	1,3-Propanediol (1,3-PDO)	PTT
Agriculture	Palm Oil	Vegetable Oil	Natural Oil Polyols (NOPs)	PUR
Agriculture	Palm Oil	Vegetable Oil	Palmitic Acid	Surfactants, Cosmetics
Agriculture	Palm Oil	Vegetable Oil	PHA	Plastics
Agriculture	Palm Oil	Vegetable Oil	Bio-based Naphtha	PE, PP
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	1,3-Propanediol (1,3-PDO)	PTT
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Isosorbide	APC
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	PHA	Plastics
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (2,5-FDCA)	PEF
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Lactid Acid	PLA
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	1,4-Butanediol (1,4-BDO)	PBT, PBAT, PBS
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Succinic Acid	PBT, PBAT, PBS
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Bio-based Ethylene	PE, PP
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Furan dicarboxylic methyl ester (FDME)	PTF
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Starch-containing polymer compounds	Starch Polymers
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Citric Acid	Surfactants, Cosmetics
Agriculture	Corn	Sugar/Starch	Paper Starch	Paper Products
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Bio-based Ethylene	PE, PP
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Lactid Acid	PLA
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Monoethylene glycol (MEG)	PEF, PET
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	PHA	Plastics
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Isosorbide	APC
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	1,4-Butanediol (1,4-BDO)	PBT, PBAT, PBS
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Succinic Acid	PBT, PBAT, PBS
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Citric Acid	Surfactants, Cosmetics
Agriculture	Sugar Cane	Sugar/Starch	Enzymes	Detergents
Agriculture	Cotton	Cellulose	Cotton lint	Cotton fabrics

Figure 5: Identified potential bio-based value chains (long list) - extract from Excel spreadsheet

Following the identification of possible value chains, this report has defined various selection criteria for the selection of five bio-based products, which will take place in the coming weeks. It is important to note that the main information and data used to define these criteria come mainly from Eurostat's PRODCOM database. PRODCOM stands for "PRODUCTION COMunaire" and is a classification of the production of goods in the EU. It is used to present information on the production and trade of products in different industrial sectors. The PRODCOM database classifies products according to the NACE classification (Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne) by assigning them a code and grouping them into classes according to their use (Eurostat 2008).

This database makes it possible to obtain not only the European production volumes of a product, but also trade volumes and production values. In addition, the NACE classification allows a broad identification of the industrial sectors relevant to this study, which are relevant to the defossilisation of the EU economy and are included in the Bioeconomy Strategy of the European Commission (2018):

- NACE class C13: *Manufacture of textiles*

- NACE class C14: *Manufacture of wearing apparel*
- NACE class C15: *Manufacture of leather and related products*
- NACE class C16: *Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials*
- NACE class C17: *Manufacture of paper and paper products*
- NACE class C20: *Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products*
- NACE class C21: *Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations*
- NACE class C22: *Manufacture of rubber and plastic products*
- NACE class C31: *Manufacture of furniture*

Values and information on the bio-based content of a final product or its bio-based production within the European bioeconomy will be taken from the work of the nova Institute and the "bio-based shares" developed in collaboration with the JRC (Joint Research Centre) (Porc et al. 2022). These "bio-based shares" are percentages that indicate the share of European bio-based production in manufactured goods. These shares are derived from stakeholder interviews, market reports and expert knowledge.

These percentages are particularly important in sectors where bio-based products are only partially available. For example, agricultural, forestry and fisheries, food, beverages, tobacco and paper products are considered to be 100% bio-based. On the other hand, textiles, forestry, chemicals, plastics and pharmaceuticals are only partially bio-based.

The following overview illustrates the different criteria that will be used to select at least 5 bio-based products for the evaluation of the certified and non-certified share. It is important to note that the selection of bio-based products has not yet been made and will be conducted during the work on deliverable D2.4 "Report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products and materials."

An overview of the selection criteria that will be used:

- Type of product:
 - Dedicated product or "smart" drop-in
- Bio-based content of the final product
 - fully bio-based
- Sector:
 - Relevance to the defossilisation of the EU economy according to the European Bioeconomy Strategy
 - NACE class (European Classification of Economic Activities)
- Bioeconomy:
 - Production in the EU:
 - Very low/none (0 – 10%)
 - Low (11 – 30%)
 - Medium (31 – 50%)
 - High (51 – 70%)
 - Very high (71 – 100%)
 - Self-sufficiency/dependence on imports
 - Low (<30%)
 - Medium (30-70%)
 - High (over 70%)
 - Production value:
 - Net value of production and trade
 - Low (<=0%)
 - Medium (0-50%)
 - High (above 50%)

The following section briefly presents the results of the application of the scoring system for the selection of suitable feedstocks for the value chains presented in section 2.1.1. The feedstocks used for this assessment were those listed in Deliverable D2.1 and are shown in the annex of this report (Table 5). Data on production and trade were taken from the recent analysis of biomass trade flows (Task 2.1). A complete overview of these results and the list of trade data will be available in Deliverable D2.4 "Report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products and material (M24)".

Below are two tables for the selection of agricultural feedstocks (Table 3) and another table for the selection of residues and waste raw materials (Table 4). However, no selection procedure was carried out for the forestry and aquaculture categories. In these categories, only one major feedstock is considered representative of the sector (forestry: wood; aquaculture: algae), as no other specific feedstocks were identified within these sectors.

Table 3 shows the selection of agricultural feedstocks. It demonstrates that starch from maize, sugar from sugar cane, palm oil and cotton were selected as raw materials for the value chains. Table 4 shows the selection of feedstocks from the processing industry and from waste. Used cooking oil, sugar beet pulp and brewers' spent grains were selected, as well as glycerol, a by-product of biodiesel production.

Table 3: Selection of agricultural feedstocks according to the scoring system – results

Origin	Feedstock Category	Feedstock and its residues	Import volume (into the EU) (mln tonnes)	Feedstock Availability in the EU (mln tonnes)	Import dependency (%)	Points –Import volume (into the EU) (mln tonnes)	Points – Feedstock Availability in the EU (mln tonnes)	Points – mport dependency (%)	Points – Total
Agriculture	Starch Crops	Corn Starch	0.06	5.28	1%	1	2	1	4
		Wheat Starch	0.01	4.42	0%	0	2	0	2
		Potato Starch	0.01	0.87	1%	0	1	1	2
	Sugar Crops	Beet Sugar	0.03	15.91	0%	0	3	0	3
		Cane Sugar	1.00	0.97	100%	3	1	5	8
	Vegetable oil Crops	Coconut oil	0.58	0.55	100%	2	1	5	8
		Groundnut oil	0.06	0.14	39%	0	1	2	3
		Oil of castor beans	0.15	0.15	100%	1	1	5	7
		Oil sesame seed	0.01	0.04	17%	0	1	1	2
		Olive oil	0.29	1.46	12%	1	2	1	3
		Palm oil	7.11	6.96	100%	5	2	5	12
		Rapeseed or canola oil	0.44	8.94	5%	1	2	1	4
		Soya bean oil	0.46	2.50	13%	1	2	1	4
		Sunflower oil	2.23	4.95	38%	4	2	2	8
		Fibre Crops	Flax	0.01	0.67	1%	0	1	1
	Hemp		0.0002	0.15	0%	0	1	0	1
	Cotton		0.23	0.26	38%	1	1	2	4

Table 4: Selection of feedstocks from processing industry and waste according to the scoring system – results

Origin	Feedstock Category	Feedstock and its residues	Import volume (into the EU) (mln tonnes)	Feedstock Availability in the EU (mln tonnes)	Import dependency (%)	Points – Import volume (into the EU) (mln tonnes)	Points – Feedstock Availability in the EU (mln tonnes)	Points – Import dependency (%)	Points – Total
Food Industry	Residues (processing industry) & Wastes	Used Cooking Oil	1.96	2.57	73%	3	2	3	8
		Sugar Beet pulp	1.19	24.94	5%	3	3	1	7
		Brewers' spent grains	0.51	8.70	6%	2	2	1	5
		Animal fat	0.05	0.79	5%	0	1	1	2
		Fruit skins/peels	0.01	2.65	0%	0	2	0	2
		Casein (non-edible milk)	0.01	0.03	13%	0	1	1	2
Transport sector		Glycerol	0.23	0.50	25%	1	1	2	4
Paper & pulp industry		Tall oil	0.16	0.68	21%	1	1	1	3
Wastes	Municipal Wastes	Organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW)	no data available	96.6	no data available	0	4	0	4

In summary, these feedstocks have been selected by feedstock category:

- *Agricultural feedstocks (4 Feedstocks)*
 - *Starch crop (1 Feedstock) → **Corn Starch***
 - *Sugar crop (1 Feedstock) → **Cane sugar***
 - *Vegetable oil crop (1 Feedstock) → **Palm oil***
 - *Fibre crop (1 Feedstock) → **Cotton***
- *Forestry feedstock (1 Feedstock) → **(industrial) Wood***

- *Aquaculture feedstock (1 Feedstock) → **Algae***
- *Feedstocks; residues from processing industry + wastes (4 Feedstocks) → **Used cooking oil, sugar beet pulp, brewers' spent grains, glycerol***

OFMSW could potentially be considered as a suitable feedstock. However, due to the lack of robust trade data for this feedstock, it was decided not to select it for further evaluation at this stage.

The mass balance approach model operates within a chain of custody framework where materials or products with specified characteristics are mixed with those without. This ensures that the proportions of specified characteristics in the input are only average and may vary between different outputs (ISO 22095:2020 2020). This approach is essential for monitoring and documenting material or product flows, particularly in the areas of certification and traceability. Under this model, the claim to a portion of the output is proportional to the amount of input materials used. For example, if 10% of the inputs are certified, a company can claim 10% of the output as certified. The use of the rolling average claim adds flexibility by allowing for variations in input volumes. It allows claims to be calculated based on an average over a period of time, thereby increasing the accuracy of the allocation used in this analysis. To assess the ratio of certified to non-certified feedstocks imported into the EU, we used a methodology based on the mass balance approach. This method aims to provide a reliable estimate by meticulously tracking the flow of certified and non-certified raw materials through the supply chain until they are imported into the EU as feedstock, intermediate or final product. However, this model can also be used to assess EU domestic production and intra-EU trade.

2.2.1 Selection of relevant countries based on trade data

In order to apply the mass balance approach to selected value chains, the first step is to identify the most relevant countries for each value chain. This is done using a multi-level approach based on trade data, starting with the three largest exporters of final products to the EU. This multi-level approach classifies each country as an exporter of final products, intermediate products, or feedstocks, depending on its position in the value chain. The first group (final product exporters) includes the three largest final product exporters to the EU, while the second group (intermediate product exporters) includes the three largest intermediate product exporters to the countries in the first group. This logic is applied until the main feedstock exporters are identified for each value chain (Figure 6). In addition, the results of the trade data analysis from Task 2.1, using production and trade data from market databases such as the FAO's FAOSTAT database or the UN's Comtrade (UNCTD), are used to provide a comprehensive overview of the trade in bio-based products and their importers in Europe. This model can also be used for intra-EU trade.

Methodological steps for selecting relevant countries based on trade data:

1. Identification of non-EU countries importing final products into the EU:
 - Analysis of trade data to identify non-EU countries exporting finished products.
2. Identifying non-EU countries exporting intermediate products:
 - Analysis of trade data to identify countries exporting intermediate products to the previously identified non-EU countries.
3. Identification of countries importing feedstocks for intermediate products:
 - Detailed analysis to identify the countries of origin of the feedstocks needed to produce intermediate products.

Figure 6: Selection of countries based on trade quantity of end product (EP), intermediate product (IM) and raw material (RM). Source: Own production.

2.2.2 Estimation of share of certified vs non-certified feedstock

To estimate certified and non-certified feedstocks, we will use the mass balance approach. In this step, we assume a direct relationship between a country's certified cultivation area or production and its export volume.

The share of certified feedstocks per country will be estimated by scouting and analysing the available databases of sustainability certification schemes identified in Work Package 1 that cover or certify the selected feedstocks. For the purpose of this study, we do not make distinction across different certification schemes. This means that the total certified area or production of a country is the result of the sum of the area or total production certified by multiple certification schemes. The objective of this step is to obtain the share of certified and non-certified feedstocks per country. The total certified share of feedstock imported to intermediate product exporter country is then the average of the top three feedstock exporter countries relevant to the value chain (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Estimation of the share of feedstock input and intermediate output that is certified

This share is then linked to the export data to an intermediate product exporter country. Part of this raw material is expected to be used within the relevant value chain; we assume that this quantity is certified in the percentage estimated before. The same logic is then applied throughout the value chain up until the EU (Figure 8Figure 9).

Figure 8: Estimation of the share of intermediate input and end-product output that is certified

Figure 9: Estimation of end-product output that is certified and imported into the EU

Methodological steps for estimating the share of certified vs. non-certified flows:

1. Identifying suitable certification schemes (SCS+Labels):
Search for certification or standard-setting organisations responsible for the certification of the selected feedstocks, taking into account the information from WPI.
2. Database search on certification schemes:
Search databases to obtain information on certified volumes from the identified countries (e.g., FSC, RSPO).
3. Determination of certification status and volumes:
Database analysis to determine certification status and volumes of feedstocks. In addition to information on certified commodity production, information on certified area is also used (e.g., 10% of palm oil area in Indonesia is certified, then it is assumed that 10% of palm oil from Indonesia is certified).
4. Application of the chain of custody model (mass balance):
Application of chain of custody model.
5. Select the three countries with the highest selected feedstock imports:
Identify the three countries with the highest feedstock import volumes.
6. Determine the percentage of certified and non-certified feedstocks:
Calculate the percentage of certified and non-certified feedstocks from the identified countries.
7. Use the average as the certified proportion:
Use the calculated average as the representative certified proportion in the production of the intermediate products.
8. Calculate the non-certified percentage:
Calculate the non-certified share as 100% minus the assumed certified share.
9. Analysis for intermediate and final products:
Repeat steps 5-8 for intermediate products, intermediate products to final products and final products imported into the EU. In addition, the potentially certified domestic production of a raw material, intermediate or final product in a country where the raw material or product lands or within the EU must also be taken into account.
10. Final result - estimated certification percentage of the final product:
Calculate the estimated certification rate of the final product imported into the EU based on the product chain model along the value chain. Note that the assessment can be carried out along the entire value chain (assessment from raw material → intermediate product → final product → EU), but also in cases where the intermediate product is imported into the EU (assessment from raw material → intermediate product → EU) or the direct import of a raw material into the EU (assessment from raw material → EU).

The initial results of the research within the STAR4BBS project highlight the significant limitations and constraints in identifying and quantifying certified biomass flows within the value chain and trade. Despite the lack of a comprehensive market database, this methodology serves as a crucial first step towards understanding these flows in the bioeconomy.

By developing a concept and methodology to link certification schemes and labels with biomass trade flows, we aim to provide a first overview of the share of certified and non-certified biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products in the EU. This analysis is primarily based on the mass balance approach, a chain of custody model.

In addition to describing the application of the mass balance approach, the report details the selection process, highlighting how data from the ongoing STAR4BBS results from Task 1.2 and 1.3 and the biomass trade flow analysis from Task 2.1 have been and will be used to identify the most appropriate value chains for quantifying certified and non-certified trade. The selection of supply chains was divided into a selection of feedstocks and a selection of bio-based products. The selection for feedstock has already been made in this report. The raw materials selected for value chains were corn starch, sugar cane, palm oil and cotton. In addition, raw materials from processing industries and wastes were selected, including used cooking oil, sugar beet pulp and brewers' spent grains, and glycerol, a by-product of biodiesel production. Wood from forestry and algae from aquaculture were also included in the selection. The final selection of the most suitable bio-based products (at least 5) will be completed in the next few weeks of the project. This will be followed by the quantification of the certified and non-certified trade.

However, it's important to note that this approach can only provide a preliminary overview as it relies on assumptions and simplifications. Data availability remains a significant challenge, with limited information on the certification status of specific bio-based products.

Despite these challenges, the methodology developed in WP2 of the STAR4BBS project will support the ongoing analysis of trade flows. In particular, it will contribute to the final report on volumes of biogenic feedstocks and bio-based products (D2.4) by providing insights into the flows of certified and non-certified biomass within and into the European bioeconomy.

Furthermore, these findings could feed into deliverable D2.5 "Impact assessment of sustainable certification schemes on market access and trade" due in project month 24. This assessment will examine the impacts and contributions of existing sustainable certification schemes and labels in enabling sustainability. It will also examine how the introduction of SCS and labels affects market access and trade dynamics within bio-based systems, and to what extent these sustainability certifications act as catalysts or barriers. By evaluating certified and non-certified flows, valuable insights can be gained into the differential impacts of certified and non-certified trade. It's important to note that beyond the scope of this project, this methodology could serve as a first step in this area and could be further refined, modified and extended in future research and modelling efforts.

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Table 5: Preliminary results of trade flow analysis (taken from deliverable D2.1 “Concept and methodology for collecting volumes of biogenic feedstock”

Feedstock Sector	Raw Biomass	European Production (Mio. t)	Production Quantity Source	Import Quantity	Export Quantity	HS-Code
Agriculture	Corn Starch	5.39	FAOSTAT	0.06	0.10	110812
Agriculture	Wheat Starch	4.09	FAOSTAT	0.01	0.09	110811
Agriculture	Cane Sugar	0.00	FAOSTAT	1.00	0.03	170111
Agriculture	Beet Sugar	15.89	FAOSTAT	0.03	0.00	170112
Agriculture	Sunflower Oil	3.59	FAOSTAT	2.23	0.89	151211
Agriculture	Palm Oil	0.00	FAOSTAT	7.11	0.15	151110
Agriculture	Wheat Straw	27.86	Own Calculation based on FAOSTAT + literature	0.08	1.67	121300
Agriculture	Cotton	0.37	FAOSTAT	0.23	0.34	520100
Forestry	Wood	191.89	FAOSTAT	9.53	15.90	440300
Residues (from Food processing)	Animal fat	0.80	PRODCOM	0.05	0.06	151610
Residues (from Food processing)	Sugar beet pulp	23.8	Own Calculation based on FAOSTAT + literature	1.19	0.09	230320
Residues (from paper and pulp industry)	Tall oil	0.60	PRODCOM	0.16	0.07	380300
Residues (from Biodiesel production)	Glycerol	0.69	PRODCOM	0.23	0.42	152000
Wastes	Used Cooking Oil	0.71	Literature (Grinsven et al. 2020)	1.96	0.10	15180095

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